

A REPORT ON THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ON MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM IN BANGLADESH

MD ESAN SARDER¹
SYEDA RUKAIA KHATUN²
MD MEHEDI HASAN³

sarderesan@gmail.com¹

syedarukaia@gmail.com²

mhmunna80808@gmail.com³

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7782-4778¹

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6074-0372²

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4239-2722³

Rajshahi University, Rajshahi, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

When we think of modern civilization, we think of technology. Technology makes our lives easier in every sphere. In every moment, we use technology directly or indirectly. It has changed the education sector very rapidly. Nowadays, teachers are providing lectures using projectors to simulate some chapters which are not always possible to be practically presented. Teachers and students have access to any books or documents via internet. As a result, they can read and gather knowledge about anything anywhere. Education is the backbone of a nation and the backbone of education system is its students. If they are on the right track then the future of the state is considered as in safe zone. Technology has changed the education system and makes it easier and more affordable for all sectors. After the outbreak of COVID-19, the education system becomes more dependent on technology. Universities and schools are taking classes via Zoom, Google Meet or in other video meeting apps. So, without technological help it is almost impossible to get in touch with the students during this lockdown. Technology has also demerits besides its benefits. Teenagers are becoming addicted in using smartphone. They are wasting their valuable time playing video games and using social. They need proper guidance to use technology. If they use technology in the right way, gathering knowledge will be enjoyable and easier to them.

Keywords: Civilization, Sphere, Rapidly, Backbone, COVID-19, Teenagers, Guidance.